

Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine

[Data](#) | May 22, 2026

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- The applied research grants, EPC-20-007 and EPC-23-024, fund the development of the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine which transforms the foundational climate and environmental data that underpins California’s Climate Change Assessment into actionable information to improve electricity sector resilience. This platform provides users with customized data, advanced analytics, and powerful cloud computing resources, allowing users to perform high-level analysis without needing to download massive localized climate datasets. Enhanced metrics that convert climate data into electricity sector specific formulations and novel analytics direct users to the most relevant scenarios for their specific applications. The cloud-based data platform provides unprecedented computational resources to users, pre-loaded with easy-to-access capacity for the transformation of climate data into stakeholder identified formats, with supporting analytics guiding users to best practices and solutions for their specific application. Continual outreach provides foundational educational training and support to users of the data platform.

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Data

Data Overview

The Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine (AE) enables access to a wide variety of data. There are multiple methods to access data that depend on individual goals and technical expertise. To understand dataset availability on the AE, please refer to the [Data Catalog](#). The Data Catalog meets strict metadata standards and receives regular updates as new sources of climate data become available on the AE.

About the data

Information on data available on the Analytics Engine (AE), including derived variables and indices, and how to contribute additional datasets to the AE.

Data Catalog

Catalog of current climate datasets available on the Analytics Engine.

Accessing data

Methods to access and download climate data on the Analytics Engine.

Metadata Standards

Metadata specifications and best practices for data use.

About the Data

Topics covered in this section:

- What **climate data** does the Analytics Engine provide?
- What **climate models, downscaling methods, and scenarios** are available in the Analytics Engine?
- What are the **Coordinate Reference Systems (CRS)** and **grid conventions** for WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid data?
- How are **datasets defined and used** in the Analytics Engine?
- What **additional data** does the Analytics Engine provide?
- What **derived variables and indices** are available on the Analytics Engine?
- What **historical model data** is available on the Analytics Engine?
- Is the data on the Analytics Engine **credible**?
- What **data challenges** are the Analytics Engine team currently aware of?
- Can users utilize **external and/or private data**?
- How can users **contribute** data or code to the Analytics Engine?

What climate data does the Analytics Engine provide?

The Analytics Engine hosts climate change projections and related data, much of which was generated for [California's Fifth Climate Change Assessment](#). The derived projections were created using two methods: 1) dynamical downscaling and 2) statistical downscaling of outputs of global climate models (GCMs) from CMIP6 (Coupled model Intercomparison Project Phase 6).

California academic institutions implement dynamical and statistical downscaling methods in support of California Energy Commission (CEC) initiatives. The dynamical downscaling data developed at [UCLA](#) utilized the Weather Research & Forecasting Model ([WRF](#)). This method created several physically-based projections available for public use and on the Analytics Engine. This data was then used to build the Localized Construct Analogs ([LOCA2](#)) at [Scripps](#). LOCA2 datasets are bias-corrected (Global Climate Model (GCM) output is adjusted to be consistent with empirical observations) using monthly mean conditions. Each of these datasets includes a variety of GCMs, variables, and Shared Socioeconomic Pathways ([SSPs](#)) for use by interested parties.

A summary of the datasets hosted on the Analytics Engine are listed in the table below; they can be viewed in detail in the [Data Catalog](#). For more information on how to access these datasets, see the [Accessing Data](#) section. For additional details on Dynamical versus Statistical downscaling approaches, see our Glossary of Terms. To understand how to use WRF and LOCA2 data to answer application-specific questions for decision making, refer to our forthcoming Guidance section. For further information on these introductory comments, refer to:

- GCMs and downscaling methods: [Carbon Brief's Q&A: How do climate models work?](#)
- Climate Data and Analytics Working Group ([C-DAWG](#))
- [01 - Bias Correction in the WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid Projections](#)
- [02 - Dynamical Downscaling using WRF](#)

- [03 - LOCA2-Hybrid \(for California\)- Training Data](#)
- [04 - Hybrid Downscaling](#)
- [05 - Hydrology Projections](#)
- [06 - Hourly Sea Level Projections from CMIP6 climate and weather](#)

What climate models, downscaling methods, and scenarios are available in the Analytics Engine?

The data available on the Analytics Engine were identified and selected through a rigorous skill evaluation process based on the parent GCM's ability to capture several critical aspects of California climate characteristics. These models were then downscaled via different complex techniques for California. More details on the GCM selection process are available [here](#).

Global Climate Models

Various CMIP6 GCMs are available, each of which may be used to explore possible future climate projections with built-in assumptions, methodologies, and limitations. We recommend, where possible, using as many GCMs in your workflows in order to capture the full range of possibilities.

Downscaling Methods

Downscaled data is available via two methods

- Downscaled by [UCLA](#) using a dynamical method with the Weather Research and Forecasting model ([WRF](#))
- Downscaled by [Scripps Institution of Oceanography](#) using a hybrid-statistical downscaling method, Localized Constructed Analogs version 2 ([LOCA2-Hybrid](#))

Spatial Resolution

- 45-km (WRF only)
- 9-km - Western Electricity Coordinating Council (WECC) region (WRF only)
- 3-km - California (CA) resolution (WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid)

Of particular note is the nuance that the 3km data is not “just” a narrowing of projections data but a qualitatively more accurate representation of the data than the 45km.

Shared Scenario Pathways

Various Shared Scenario Pathways (SSPs) representing global emissions trajectories from intermediate to higher trajectories are available on the Analytics Engine for the LOCA2-Hybrid data. SSP2-4.5, SSP3-7.0, and SSP5-8.5 each represent a combination of narratives (2, 3, and 5) and Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) (4.5, 7.0, and 8.5). For example, SSP2-4.5 utilizes the SSP 2 narrative and RCP 4.5. All the WRF runs use SSP3-7.0.

What are the Coordinate Reference Systems (CRS) and grid conventions for WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid data?

WRF Data

The CRS for WRF data on the Analytics Engine is Lambert Conformal Conic, a common projection used with WRF. WRF datasets include a `grid_mapping` attribute that references a `Lambert_Conformal` coordinate variable, which contains the full projection details. The WRF data is not identified by a standard EPSG code or datum because the WRF projection is based on a spherical Earth. For more information on WRF projections, see this [blog post](#).

LOCA2-Hybrid Data

The CRS for LOCA2-Hybrid data on the Analytics Engine is WGS84 (World Geodetic System 1984), a standard geographic coordinate system. Unlike WRF, LOCA2-Hybrid datasets do not include a `grid_mapping` attribute. Instead, CRS information is stored in a `spatial_ref` coordinate variable at the global level, which contains the full coordinate system details including the WGS84 datum.

How are datasets defined and used in the Analytics Engine?

Downscaled simulations of California's climate

The climate projections hosted on the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine are regional simulations over the Western United States and California, produced by downscaling Global Climate Models (GCM) from the sixth iteration of the Climate Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP6). These downscaled simulations were created in support of [California's Fifth Climate Change Assessment](#), and detailed information about the models used and the data produced can be found in the [Data section](#).

Additional data sources for calculating data on Global Warming Levels

When using the Analytics Engine to calculate climate variables at [global warming levels](#), data from two additional sources are utilized in the calculations: the CMIP6 archive hosted by Pangeo, and data from the IPCC AR6 Report. A detailed methodology of how this data is used will be included in an upcoming section "How California-focused Warming Level Time Series are Calculated", and additional guidance on how to incorporate global warming levels into planning is given [here](#).

Warming level years from global GCM runs

Global warming levels are defined as the average increase in global surface air temperature relative to pre-industrial conditions (1850-1900). Combining data from several climate simulations around the years that each one reaches specified global warming levels provides a clear standard of measuring how regional impacts will scale with different levels of global warming. Because the WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid simulations in the Analytics Engine are run only over the Western US they can not be used to evaluate

global temperature, so data from the parent GCM simulations is used to determine the range of years from each simulation that corresponds to a given global warming level.

For this calculation, the Analytics Engine utilizes a publicly available archive of CMIP6 simulations [hosted on AWS by the Pangeo project](#).

GWL timing for scenarios overall

One of the benefits of analyzing projections of climate change on global warming levels is that years for warming level estimates can be estimated independently from the trajectories of the GCMs themselves. This is particularly beneficial because the CMIP6 models are known to have a much [wider range in their climate sensitivity](#), which introduces significant uncertainty into estimates of when each warming level will be reached.

Because of this, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) draws in data from a variety of other scientific studies including observational constraints and climate emulators to produce a refined estimate of likely warming trajectories under each climate scenario. Details about the inputs to these likely trajectories are described in the [4th chapter](#) of IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), and an overview of the resulting best estimates and ranges are provided in the [Technical Summary](#).

When using warming levels, the Analytics Engine provides estimates for the crossing year and very likely range (90% confidence interval) based on the [publicly available data](#) used in the IPCC report.

Figure 1. Best estimate and 90% confidence interval for the year the world will reach 2.0 °C of warming under the SSP 3-7.0 scenario. The median year of crossing is denoted by the vertical dashed line and is provided. The solid lines represent the first and last occurrence of the 5th and 95th percentiles crossing the designated warming level,

with the range in years provided. For example, the median year of GCMs reaching 2.0°C of warming is in 2047, with a range of 24 years between the first and last occurrence. Figure produced by the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine based on data from the IPCC.

Global warming level year exceedance and range (Surface air temperature increase relative to 1850-1900)								
	1.5°C		2.0°C		2.5°C		3.0°C	
	Best Estimate	Very Likely Range (5-95%)						
SSP 1-2.6	2033	2024-2100+	-	-	-	-	-	-
SSP 2-4.5	2031	2024-2043	2053	2039-2081	2080	2054-2100+	-	-
SSP 3-7.0	2031	2024-2041	2047	2037-2061	2062	2049-2080	2076	2060-2097
SSP 5-8.5	2028	2022-2037	2042	2034-2054	2054	2044-2069	2065	2053-2083

Table 1. Summary of best estimates and ranges for crossing reaching global warming levels under each SSP scenario. Summarized from data from the IPCC.

For more information on fetching global warming level data in the Analytics Engine, or how California-focused warming level data is calculated, check out our [Methods page](#).

What additional data does the Analytics Engine provide?

In addition to hosting dynamical and hybrid-statistical downscaled climate datasets, the Analytics Engine also hosts vector datasets containing administrative boundaries, hydrologic boundaries, and key regions of interest to the energy sector. Within the Jupyter notebooks available on the Analytics Engine, the below vector datasets can be used to select, view, aggregate, and summarize climate data for a geography of interest:

- California counties
- Watersheds (HUC10)
- California Electricity Demand Forecast Zones
- California Electric Balancing Authority Areas
- Investor- and public-owned electrical utility service territories
- State boundaries

What derived variables and indices are available on the Analytics Engine?

In addition to the climate variables available on the Analytics Engine, several derived variables and indices may be of interest. From a computation standpoint, there is no difference between a derived variable and an index in their construction - they both calculate a new variable based on input variables. However, an index usually has a “next step of interpretation” (e.g. a public safety warning may be issued when Heat Index exceeds 80°F). A derived variable expands the available variable list beyond the native variables within the data.

- [Specific humidity](#): the amount of water vapor within a unit amount of air.
- [Heating and cooling degree days](#): a measure of how cold or warm a location is in reference to a standard temperature; heating degree days are indicative of how much lower the ambient temperature is from the standard temperature; cooling degree days are indicative of how much higher the temperature is above the threshold temperature. A common standard temperature threshold for heating/cooling degree days is 65°F.
 - Heating and cooling degree days and hours are accessible through *climakitae* functions. The computation and interpretation demonstration can be found in the [annual_consumption_model.ipynb](#) Jupyter Notebook.
- [Heating and cooling degree hours](#): similar to heating and cooling degree days, heating and cooling degree hours represent the number of hours in each day of how warm or cold a location is in reference to a standard temperature threshold. Heating degree hours are the number of hours that are lower than the reference temperature threshold, while cooling degree hours are the number of hours that are higher than the reference temperature threshold.

Derived Indices

- [Effective temperature](#): half of the prior day’s temperature added to half of the current day’s actual temperature; the metric takes into account the previous day’s air temperature to consider consumer behavior and perception of weather.
- [NOAA Heat Index](#): a measure of how hot weather “actually feels” on the body by accounting for air temperature and humidity.
 - The [heat_index.ipynb](#) Jupyter Notebook provides a walkthrough describing how to retrieve and interpret NOAA Heat Index values.
- [Fosberg Fire Weather Index](#): provides a quantitative assessment of weather impacts on fire management.

Each of the derived index options and specific humidity are available through the select function within the Jupyter notebooks, which displays the “Choose Data Available with the Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine” panel by selecting “Derived Index”.

Choose Data Available with the Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine

Data type:

Gridded

Downscaling method:

Dynamical

Variable:

Variable **Derived Index**

Fosberg fire weather index ▼

9 km

What historical model data is available on the Analytics Engine?

The Analytics Engine provides two types of downscaled data in the historical climate period (1980-2014): reanalysis datasets and global climate model historical runs. Although they appear similar, each dataset has a unique use within a planning context.

The differences between these historical datasets are explored in the [historical climate data comparisons notebook](#).

Reanalysis datasets

Referred to as “Historical Reconstruction” in the Analytics Engine

Reanalysis products are reconstructions of the historical weather record that combine model data with historical observational data. Reanalysis products synthesize disparate sources of observational data and use an atmospheric model to produce a spatiotemporally continuous, self-consistent dataset, avoiding the gaps and data collection inconsistencies in weather station data. Like a climate model, reanalysis products have a complete set of atmospheric and surface weather variables on a full spatial grid. This quality makes reanalysis an essential tool for climate scientists when evaluating and bias correcting climate model simulations.

The Analytics Engine contains data from the ERA5 reanalysis dataset that has been dynamically downscaled to 3km resolution over California. This dataset allows users to study the historical record or specific meteorological events like heatwaves and droughts.

Historical runs from Global Climate models

Referred to as “Historical Climate” in the Analytics Engine

Historical runs of Global Climate Models (GCMs) are simulations that use the historical record of greenhouse gas concentrations as inputs. Using combined simulations of the atmosphere, ocean, and land surface, GCMs produce a physically consistent timeline of plausible climate conditions over the historical period. Unlike reanalysis data, these simulations do not reproduce specific events from the historical record, but instead represent the general conditions during that time period.

Each simulation from a climate model produces unique weather events and represents the internal variability of the climate system slightly differently. When climate models are used to simulate future conditions, this variability between realizations can help determine the range of potential future realities. When climate models are run over the historical period, the variability across model realizations represents the range of possible conditions that could have occurred.

When calculating change signals between the past and future climate, the historical data from GCM runs provides an essential baseline to characterize climate change in each model. Because each climate model has a unique physical representation of the world, climate change signals are the most accurate when calculated relative to the historical period of the same climate model.

The Analytics Engine contains simulations over the historical period for all of the dynamically (WRF) and statistically (LOCA2) downscaled climate simulations. Because the latest generation of underlying GCMs were run starting in 2016, the historical period for models in the Analytics Engine runs through 2014, after which the simulations split into estimated future scenarios. The WRF simulations have a historical period of 1980-2014, and the LOCA2 historical simulations extend from 1950-2014.

A note on comparing reanalysis with historical climate simulations:

To evaluate how well climate models represent particular features of the climate, it can be very useful to compare historical climate simulations to reanalysis. When making these comparisons, it is important to remember that the climate model data will not match the year-to-year historical record in the reanalysis data. Instead, comparisons should be made by aggregating data over a sufficiently long time period (typically at least 30 years) that samples the range of the climate's natural variability.

How does the data handle leap years?

GCMs come in a variety of calendars for handling the time dimension: including “fixed 365 day” (no leap days), “proleptic Gregorian” (leap days), or even “fixed 360 day” (every month has 30 days)! Depending on your analysis, you may wish to either keep or remove leap days for consistency with best practices. For example, in bias adjustment localization, leap days should be removed.

In the WRF models:

- No leap days: CESM2, FGOALS-g3, TaiESM1
- Leap days: EC-Earth3-Veg, CNRM-ESM2-1, EC-Earth3, MIROC6, and MPI-ESM1-2-HR

In the LOCA2-Hybrid models, all models were interpolated to include leap days if the parent GCM did not natively retain leap days. For more information on leap days in the LOCA2-Hybrid models, please see this [blog post](#).

Is the data on the Analytics Engine credible?

All of the downscaled data available on the Analytics Engine comes from models that have undergone rigorous skill evaluation in terms of how well they capture specific relevant characteristics of California's climate. These models perform well for both process-based and local climate metrics ([Dynamical Downscaling memo](#)) and are able to simulate key physical processes and patterns that strongly influence

the hydrological cycle and extreme weather in California. They are also able to capture local climatic patterns such as annual and seasonal temperature and precipitation patterns. This state-level model evaluation and assessment, described in [Krantz et al. 2021](#), is unique to California and lends credibility to the data hosted on the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine.

Although all the models on the Analytics Engine are skilled at representing California's climate, not all models perform equally well for any specific sub-region within California, or for any given metric (particularly ones that the models were not specifically evaluated for). Therefore the Analytics Engine also provides tools and guidance (see the Guidance section) to help a user conduct additional, context-specific credibility analyses, such as examining the skill of the data or models for their specific region, metric, and/or application.

What data challenges are the Analytics Engine team currently aware of?

The Analytics Engine team is actively addressing data challenges and preparing up-to-date information. Users are advised to exercise caution when using the data until further details are provided.

- LOCA2-Hybrid precipitation output is too low

Initial Guidance for Biases in Relative humidity

The downscaled climate models (both WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid) produced for California's Fifth Climate Change Assessment, which is available through the [Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine](#), originates from an international scientific endeavor called [CMIP6](#). The GCMs comprising [CMIP6](#) are projecting more near surface moisture than has previously been observed and measured. In essence, this higher near surface moisture may be translating to higher relative humidity and water vapor in the downscaled climate information for the Fifth Climate Change Assessment. Given this systematic issue, it is believed that future predictions of climate will likely also predict more near surface moisture than is likely to occur. Here, we briefly describe the key problems with the models, provide user guidance as to how to use the information as is, and discuss how the Cal-Adapt team will be responding to this issue.

Key Scientific Issue: - In recent years as the climate has warmed, measurements of water vapor and relative humidity across the Southwestern United States have held relatively constant or even slightly declined over time. Climate models run over the recent past have however projected that water vapor content would have increased instead. This suggests that models are failing to properly resolve the historical hydroclimate of the Southwestern United States, including the inland area of California. - Climate models project a continued increase in the amount of atmospheric water vapor in coming decades as the Earth warms. It's unclear if this will actually happen. Scientists are concerned that climate models are over-estimating the amount of water vapor in future years. - Model errors are largest in more arid regions, and tend to be greatest in the dry / hot season. - An over-estimation of water vapor has impacts to California's energy systems, especially if models contain too much moisture, predictions of wildfire may underrepresent the frequency and intensity of fires. Predictions of measures of heat impacts which include variables like relative humidity (such as heat index or apparent temperature) may overstate the heat impact.

Key Citation: I.R. Simpson, K.A. McKinnon, D. Kennedy, D.M. Lawrence, F. Lehner, & R. Seager, Observed humidity trends in dry regions contradict climate models, Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A. 121 (1) e2302480120, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2302480120> (2024).

User Guidance: Downscaled GCM data contained in the Fifth Climate Change Assessment should not be used for wildfire modeling efforts. - Bias adjustment of data is suggested before use for quantitative assessments conducting a climatology evaluation using historical data is a crucial first step to characterize potential issues with water vapor in projections. - Downscaled GCM data can continue to be used for evaluations of extreme heat, given that the heat index calculation response curve is relatively insensitive to a 4% offset of humidity in typical heat events in California.

How Cal-Adapt is Responding: In Fall of 2025, we will perform an evaluation of the impact of this modeling issue, specifically on evaluations of extreme heat.

- The role of bias adjustment on potential bias will be quantified and described.
- We will make recommendations for how this information should be used, and potentially provide approaches to correct the issues.
- We will publicly share our findings, recommendations, and potential approaches by listing them on the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine Website, Guidance Materials, and where appropriate, incorporate into the Jupyter Notebooks and *climakitae* package.

How To Get Further Help: Energy sector stakeholders may contact analytics@cal-adapt.org for further information and support in using these projections. Non-energy sector stakeholders should contact the [Governor's Office of Land Use and Climate Innovation](#) for climate services.

Can users utilize external and/or private data on the Analytics Engine?

Yes, users are provided with a private directory space in the JupyterHub as a workspace associated with their account. Users retain this workspace between sessions and any data uploaded to the workspace is inaccessible to other users.

How can users contribute data or code to the Analytics Engine?

The Analytics Engine team welcomes users to submit data for consideration for inclusion in the [Data Catalog](#). Please submit a request via email to analytics@cal-adapt.org. These requests will be considered on a case-by-case basis depending on size, quality, and relationship to other funded work. All datasets must comply with [CF conventions](#), as outlined in our [Metadata Standards](#).

Data Catalog

Analytics Engine Data Catalog

The following tables show a list of all raw projections data available on the Analytics Engine. This includes future climate projections and historical climate downscaled from Global Climate Models (GCMs) and a historical reconstruction (reanalysis data based on modeling and empirical weather observations).

Note: The different datasets are very nuanced, and they are not interchangeable. Please review our upcoming Guidance documentation to understand the available data in full.

Details of Available Data

Data Foundation

This table demonstrates the underlying data created by our colleagues at Scripps Institution of Oceanography and UCLA, highlighting the method of downscaling, model availability, and bias correction:

Dynamically Downscaled / WRF	Hybrid-Statistically Downscaled / LOCA2-Hybrid
Institution: UCLA	Institution: Scripps
Models: 8 Unique Models CESM2, CNRM-ESM2-1, EC-Earth3, EC-Earth3-Veg, FGOALS-g3, MIROC6, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, TaiESM1	Models: 15 Unique Models ACCESS-CM2, CESM2-LENS, CNRM-ESM2-1, EC-Earth3, EC-Earth3-Veg, FGOALS-g3, GFDL-ESM4, HadGEM-GC31-LL, INM-CM5-0, IPSL-CM6A-LR, KACE-1-0-G, MIROC, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, TaiESM1
Bias Correction*: A priori: EC-Earth3, EC-Earth3-Veg, MIROC6, TaiESM1, MPI-ESM1-2-HR Other models are not bias-corrected	Bias correction*: All 15 models
Native resolution: Hourly	Native resolution: Daily
Other pre-aggregated daily and monthly datasets are available via the data catalog * Details of the bias correction method are available here .	

Downscaled Data

The following table showcases data available within Analytics Engine products, including, but not limited to, the Data Catalog and accessible via JupyterHub notebooks.

Hybrid-Statistical Downscaled Data: LOCA2-Hybrid

This downscaling method created data for 15 GCMs with a total of 199 ensemble runs.

The following table shows the LOCA2-Hybrid data constituents available by variable:

- Per SSP there are two counts
 - **GCM** is the count of GCMs that were downscaled that have that variable in at least one ensemble run
 - **Ensembles** is the count of ensemble runs that contain that variable
- All LOCA2-Hybrid data is downscaled at a native daily resolution. A pre-aggregated version of the LOCA2-Hybrid data at monthly resolution is also available on the Analytics Engine.

		Total precipitation (pr)	Max air temperature at 2m (tasmax)	Min air temperature at 2m (tasmin)	Specific humidity at 2m (huss)	Max relative humidity (hursmax)	Min relative humidity (hursmin)	Wind speed at 10m (wspeed)	West-east component of wind (uas)	North-south component of wind (vas)	Shortwave flux at the surface (rsds)
Historical	GCMs	15	15	15	13	13	13	11	11	11	14
	Ensembles	70	70	70	51	51	51	46	46	46	51
SSP2-4.5	GCMs	14	14	14	12	12	12	11	11	11	14
	Ensembles	33	33	33	25	25	25	24	24	24	30
SSP3-7.0	GCMs	14	14	14	12	12	12	10	10	10	13
	Ensembles	62	62	62	45	45	45	38	38	38	45
SSP5-8.5	GCMs	13	13	13	11	11	11	11	11	11	13
	Ensembles	34	34	34	25	25	25	26	26	26	29

Dynamical Downscaled Data: WRF

This downscaling method created data for 8 GCMs with 1 ensemble run in each emissions scenario.

The following table shows the WRF data simulations available:

- There are two kinds of WRF simulations
 - **Projections Simulations** is the count of GCMs that were downscaled per emissions scenario and spatial resolution
 - **Reanalysis Simulations** is a downscaled ensemble run of the ERA5 reanalysis dataset providing an observationally constrained historical reconstruction
- All WRF data is downscaled at a native hourly resolution.

* The Analytics Engine also provides a pre-aggregated version of the WRF data at daily (noted by asterisk) and monthly resolutions for four of the WRF simulations.

** Additional simulations from 1 model (CESM2) for SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 at 9 km spatial resolution are also available on the Analytics Engine. These simulations are a part of the larger suite of dynamically downscaled GCMs by UCLA, of which the CEC-supported simulations are a subset. More information is available [here](#).

Simulations				
Projections Simulations				
		Emissions Scenario	Temporal Resolution	
			Daily*	Hourly
Spatial Resolutions	3 km (CA)	Historical	8	8
		SSP2-4.5	0	0
		SSP3-7.0	8	8
		SSP5-8.5	0	0
	9 km (WECC)	Historical	8	8
		SSP2-4.5**	1	1
		SSP3-7.0	8	8
		SSP5-8.5	1	1
	45 km	Historical	8	8
		SSP2-4.5	1	1

		SSP3-7.0	8	8
		SSP5-8.5	1	1
Reanalysis Simulations				
Spatial Resolutions	3 km (CA)	Historical Reconstruction WRF_ERA5	1	1
	9 km (WECC)		1	1
	45 km		1	1
Variables: Air temperature, wind speed, total precipitation, relative humidity, solar radiation, + 19 others				

Accessing Data

Topics covered in this section:

- Overview
- Data Structure and Format
- How can users access, visualize, and download climate data from the Analytics Engine?

Overview

The source climate projections produced for California’s Fifth Climate Change Assessment that underlie the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine (CA: AE) are freely available and accessible to the public. The projections can be accessed through Amazon’s Registry of Open Data and are hosted on Amazon Web Services (AWS) as part of the data catalog for the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine’s [“Co-Produced Climate Data to Support California’s Resilience Investments.”](#)

The Open Data program democratizes access by making data publicly available, enabling the use of cloud-optimized datasets, techniques, and tools in cloud-native formats, and building communities that benefit from these shared datasets. Because the Analytics Engine is part of the Open Data program, all climate projections are accessible now.

AE hosts nearly 1 petabyte (1000 terabytes) of multi-dimensional array data, and the size and complexity of this data make it important to become familiar with the structure of the data before trying to access or download.

Data Structure and Format

The CA: AE public AWS S3 bucket named cadcat, short for Cal-Adapt: Data Catalog, contains dynamically downscaled [WRF](#) data in Zarr and statistically downscaled [LOCA2-hybrid](#) data in both NetCDF and Zarr formats, along with other datasets such as station data (HadISD). More detailed information about the climate data used by the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine can be found in the [About the Data](#) section.

NetCDF Files

The raw LOCA2-Hybrid datasets are stored as NetCDF files in S3 at the subdirectory [LOCA2/aaa-ca-hybrid](#). The advantage of NetCDF files is that they are single files stored in a directory structure, and can thus be manually downloaded using a web browser for a minimal set of data. The disadvantage of NetCDF is that they need to be loaded completely into memory to access even a slice of the data, which can be resource exhaustive or even prohibitive.

Zarr Stores

The majority of the climate data for the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine stored on AWS S3 is in a cloud-optimized multi-dimensional array format known as Zarr. Zarr stores can be randomly accessed to retrieve a slice of the data and do not require that the entire dataset be loaded into memory. This is vitally important when dealing with hourly data over large spatial and temporal extents. The Zarrs are

stored in S3 in a hierarchical directory structure designed to work in conjunction with [Intake ESM](#) to make the data discoverable, searchable, and easier to access. The directory structure is prescribed by the Intake ESM system and can be non-intuitive to users not familiar with it. Zarr stores have many directory levels, which make it difficult to download manually using a web browser. Either the use of AWS's command line interface (AWS CLI) for S3 or Python programming is needed to access and/or download the data in this format. A web browser can be helpful in understanding the data structure before attempting to access specific files. AWS allows users to browse S3 buckets via a web browser - here is the top level of the cadcat bucket [AWS S3 Explorer](#).

There are 4 main collections of Zarr datasets in the S3 bucket:

1. WRF - Dynamically-downscaled global climate models performed by the Weather Research and Forecasting model
2. LOCA2-Hybrid - Statistically-downscaled global climate models performed by LOCA (Localized Constructed Analogs) version 2 for California
3. HadISD - Hadley Centre observations datasets (station data). Does not conform to the Intake ESM data structure, and is not part of the Intake ESM data catalog.
4. HistWxStns - Historical observation datasets (station data), including the HadISD stations.

WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid follow similar directory structures with some notable differences:

- LOCA2-Hybrid has an additional level (Variant/member_id)
- Not all parameters are the same between WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid
- Parameters are not always internally consistent.

More advanced query tools are useful in figuring out where the data is and how to load it into different software packages. The AE searchable [Data Catalog](#) was generated from the contents of the Intake ESM catalog to help identify the exact path to the data of interest. Users can type into the search box to identify datasets of interest and view the path to those datasets in the S3 bucket structure.

How can users access, visualize, and download climate data on the Analytics Engine?

Once a user has identified a specific dataset of interest, there are many ways to access, visualize, and download that data from the Analytics Engine (AE). A variety of ways to access AE data are detailed below:

Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine JupyterHub

Energy-sector users with a [Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine JupyterHub](#) login can access co-produced, pre-developed Jupyter notebooks to analyze, subset, and utilize existing Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine data. The code and data can be customized for individual needs through the JupyterHub web interface, which provides private cloud storage through Amazon Web Services. Users can then export data in a variety of formats to cloud storage or a local machine. This solution requires a Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine login, although all AE notebook code is open source and publicly available via our [cae-notebooks](#) GitHub repository.

Best Use

The Analytics Engine JupyterHub is currently exclusively provided to energy-sector partners in California, in alignment with funding from the California Energy Commission. The JupyterHub environment is hosted in AWS and has access to cluster processing, 32GB of RAM, 10GB of storage on the Hub instance, and access to S3 storage for exporting larger datasets. It can be used to do any data processing on the CA:AE of interest.

Limitations

Not yet accessible to the general public. Limited to the resources provided by the HUB instance.

Example Usage

To support a range of workflows, AE provides [data access notebooks](#) that demonstrate various methods, including direct code-based access using [climakitae](#), an intuitive graphical user interface (GUI) using the add-on package, [climakitaegui](#), and options for accessing data outside of the AE environment.

Accessing or downloading data using the climakitae Python package

A powerful Python toolkit for climate data retrieval and analysis has been developed as part of the AE project, *climakitae*. The main features of the toolset are:

- Comprehensive Climate Data Access: Retrieve climate variables from hosted climate models
- Downscaled Climate Models: Access dynamical (WRF) and statistical (LOCA2) downscaling methods
- Spatial Analysis Tools: Built-in support for geographic subsetting and spatial aggregation
- Climate Indices: Calculate heat indices, warming levels, and extreme event metrics
- Flexible Data Export: Export to NetCDF, CSV, and Zarr
- GUI Integration: Works seamlessly with *climakitaegui* for interactive analysis

Climakitae includes built-in methods to aid in the retrieval of data from the cadcat S3 bucket that are more intuitive and user-friendly than using the Python intake package directly..

Best Use

Powerful functionality allows users to retrieve data by warming level, by spatial and/or temporal filtering, by spatial and/or temporal aggregation, by derived variable, or by concatenated timeseries for historical and future scenarios. Allows users to utilize all of the CA: AE software functionality contained within the CA: AE JupyterHUB, especially when combined with the notebooks developed for the HUB in the cae-notebooks repository.

Limitations

Limited to the resources on the local computer (RAM, CPU, network), dataset processed from the original (simulations and time series concatenated, metadata added, warming levels calculated).

Example Usage

Specifically, the `get_data` function allows users to specify filtering parameters to get just the information needed instead of entire datasets, which helps ease the data size limitations of CMIP6 data.

To get started, users will need to set up a conda Python environment ([pip](#) environments are possible but harder to setup) with the necessary Python libraries. This [README](#) was created to help set up the environment. The basic steps are installing conda, downloading a curated list of supporting libraries, creating a new environment with those, and then downloading and installing *climakitae*. Once setup in the conda environment, run Python and enter these commands:

None

```
from climakitae.core.data_interface import get_data
```

This loads the `get_data` function from the package. The function has the following input parameters:

Parameter	Description	Example
variable (required)	String name of climate variable	"Air temperature at 2m", "Maximum air temperature", etc.
resolution (required)	Resolution of data in kilometers	"3 km", "9 km", or "45 km"
timescale (required)	Temporal frequency of dataset	"hourly", "daily", or "monthly"
downscaling_method (required)	Downscaling method of the data	"Dynamical" (WRF), "Statistical" (LOCA2-Hybrid), "Dynamical+Statistical" (Both)
data_type	Whether to choose gridded data or weather station data	"Gridded", or "Stations"
approach	Time based or Warming Level based	"Time", or "Warming Level"

scenario	SSP scenario and/or historical data selection	“SSP 3-7.0”, “SSP 2-4.5”, “SSP 5-8.5” “Historical Climate”, “Historical Reconstruction”
units	Variable units	Defaults to native
area_subset	Area category	“CA counties”
cached_area	Area	“Alameda county”
area_average	Take an average over spatial domain?	“Yes”, or “No”
latitude	Tuple of valid latitude bounds	(32, 36)
longitude	Tuple of valid longitude bounds	(-132, -128)
time_slice	Time range for retrieved data	(2045, 2075)
stations	Which weather station to retrieve localized downscaled model data at	KSAC (Sacramento Airport)
warming_level	Must be one of the warming levels available in <code>clmakitae.core.constants</code>	
warming_level_window	Years around Global Warming Level (+/-) \n (e.g. 15 means a 30yr window)	
warming_level_months	Months of year for which to perform warming level computation	

all_touched	Spatial subset option for within or touching selection	True, or False
enable_hidden_vars	Return all variables, including the ones in which "show" is set to False?	True or False

This list is exhaustive. Most analyses require only a small sub-set of these options. They are there to allow for the production of all the datasets needed for the Analytics Engine code and notebooks.

Another way to get the list of parameters just listed is to query the function documentation at the Python command line:

```
None
from climakitae.core.data_interface import get_data
print(get_data.__doc__)
```

A simple example of how to use this function is:

```
None
from climakitae.core.data_interface import get_data
data = get_data(
    variable="Air Temperature at 2m",
    downscaling_method="Dynamical",
    resolution="9 km",
    timescale="monthly",
    scenario="SSP 3-7.0",
    cached_area="CA"
)
```

This will retrieve the WRF Air Temperature (t2) variable as an xarray DataArray for scenario SSP 3-7.0, at 9 km resolution, and on a monthly timescale for the whole state of California. To help with analysis, the data is transformed somewhat, so if users are interested in the raw data then the AWS CLI, or intake methods are recommended. For a lookup table of variable names used by the get_data function, see [Variable Descriptions](#).

There are a few helper functions that go along with `get_data` to help understand what is available to retrieve from the data store. The `get_data_options` function returns a pandas DataFrame (table object) of the data options:

```
None
from climakitae.core.data_interface import get_data_options
get_data_options()
```

The returned Pandas DataFrame contains the fields `downscaling_method`, `scenario`, `timescale`, `variable`, and `resolution`. It is very similar to the [Data Catalog](#) found on the CA: AE website.

Using the `get_data_options` function with no parameters returns the entire list of datasets. Users can specify optional parameters to query the data catalog and find a more refined set of data.

```
None
from climakitae.core.data_interface import get_data_options
get_data_options(
    downscaling_method = "Statistical", # LOCA2-Hybrid
    resolution = "3 km"
)
```

This will refine the returned DataFrame to only the datasets matching the criteria. As another example to specify daily precipitation datasets:

```
None
get_data_options(
    variable = "precipitation", # not a variable name, but close
    timescale = "daily"
)
```

The “precipitation” string entered actually does not exactly match any variable name in the data catalog, but the command will provide this information and suggest closely matching variable names. It will also default to one of those variables and return values for it. This suggestion logic applies to the other queryable fields as well.

Another helper function, `get_subsetting_options`, is used to spatially subset the data retrieved. There is a separate data catalog that stores Adobe parquet geospatial files that store the geometries for states, CA counties, CA Electricity Demand Forecast Zones, CA Watersheds, CA Electric Balancing Authority Areas,

CA Electric Load Serving Entities, and Stations. For example, to get a list of counties available, use this command:

```
None
from climakitae.core.data_interface import get_subsetting_options
get_subsetting_options(area_subset = "CA counties")
```

This returns a Pandas DataFrame containing a list of `cached_area` values that can be used to spatially filter results when using `get_data`.

Return to `get_data` and apply some of the knowledge gained by using the helper functions `get_data_options` and `get_subsetting_options`. The minimum required inputs to `get_data` are: `variable`, `resolution`, and `timescale`. Optionally, users can spatially subset with: `area_subset`, `cached_area`, and `area_average` (set to "Yes" to aggregate the data to the selected geometry). Additionally, users can set the downscaling method, approach (Time or Warming Level), scenario, units, `time_slice`, `warming_level`, `warming_level_window`, and/or `warming_level_months`.

As an example of a time-based approach, request monthly 3 km resolution statistically downscaled historical precipitation using the following command:

```
None
data = get_data(
    variable = "Precipitation (total)",
    downscaling_method = "Statistical", # LOCA2-Hybrid
    resolution = "3 km",
    timescale = "monthly",
    scenario = "Historical Climate"
    # approach = "Time" # Optional because "Time" is the function
    default
)
```

Apply a spatial filter simply by setting the `cached_area` parameter, and then calculate the area average by using the `area_average` parameter:

```
None
data = get_data(
    variable = "Precipitation (total)",
```



```
downscaling_method = "Statistical",
resolution = "3 km",
timescale = "monthly",
scenario = "Historical Climate",

# Modify location settings
cached_area = "San Bernardino County",
area_average = "Yes"
)
```

Alternatively, to retrieve WRF precipitation for a specific time period and several scenarios:

```
None
data = get_data(
    variable = "Precipitation (total)",
    downscaling_method = "Dynamical", # WRF
    resolution = "45 km",
    timescale = "monthly",
    cached_area = "San Bernardino County",

    # Modify time-based settings
    time_slice = (2000,2050),
    scenario = [
        "Historical Climate",
        "SSP 3-7.0",
        "SSP 2-4.5",
        "SSP 5-8.5"
```



```
]
)
```

Now, retrieve the data at a warming level instead of using the time-based approach. By default the 2.0 warming level is returned:

```
None
get_data(
  variable = "Precipitation (total)",
  downscaling_method = "Dynamical", # WRF
  resolution = "45 km",
  timescale = "monthly",
  cached_area = "San Bernardino County",

  # Modify your approach
  approach = "Warming Level",
)
```

By default, a window of +/- 15 years is used to determine the warming level data retrieved. To modify the time window for a 20-year window and retrieve specific warming levels, do the following:

```
None
data = get_data(
  variable = "Precipitation (total)",
  downscaling_method = "Dynamical",
  resolution = "45 km",
  timescale = "monthly",
  cached_area = "San Bernardino County",
  approach = "Warming Level",
```



```
# Modify warming level settings
warming_level_window = 10,
warming_level = [2.5, 3.0, 4.0]
)
```

The `get_data` function by default retrieves gridded data, but users can retrieve dynamically-downscaled climate data at the unique grid cell(s) corresponding to a desired historical weather station(s) that has undergone additional localization (i.e., bias-adjustment) to that weather station. This data can be retrieved using the `data_type` and `stations` arguments. If the `stations` argument is not set, the function will return all available weather stations—a hefty data retrieval that takes a while to run and is not recommended. Localization of climate models for historical weather station data is only available for Air Temperature. To retrieve data for a single station:

```
None
data = get_data(
    variable = "Air Temperature at 2m", # Required argument
    resolution = "9 km", # Required argument. Options: "9 km" or "3
km"
    timescale = "hourly", # Required argument
    data_type = "Stations", # Required argument
    stations = "San Diego Lindbergh Field (KSAN)" # Optional
argument
)
```

Here is a more complex retrieval that retrieves two stations for a five-year period and returns the data in degrees Fahrenheit instead of Celsius:

```
None
data = get_data(
    variable = "Air Temperature at 2m",
    resolution = "3 km",
    timescale = "hourly",
```



```
data_type = "Stations",
stations = [
    "San Francisco International Airport (KSFO)",
    "Oakland Metro International Airport (KOAK)",
],
units = "degF",
time_slice = (2000,2005)
)
```

Users can also retrieve localized station data for future scenarios. The following command retrieves both the historical and SSP 3-7.0 scenarios for the time period 2000-2035:

```
None
data = get_data(
    variable = "Air Temperature at 2m",
    resolution = "9 km",
    timescale = "hourly",
    data_type = "Stations",
    stations = "Sacramento Executive Airport (KSAC)",
    units = "degF",
    time_slice = (2000,2035),
    scenario = ["Historical Climate", "SSP 3-7.0"]
)
```

Upon data retrieval, the historical and future SSP data are combined into a single timeseries for ease of use, rather than two separate data objects representing each time period individually. The localization procedure uses the historical weather station data to accurately bias-adjust the historical period, which is then applied to the SSP data.

To export (save the data to local storage) the DataArray returned by `get_data`, use either the `xarray` export functions or `climakitae`, which includes a built-in export function that handles metadata and formatting issues. The S3 saving option is reserved for users of the CA: AE JupyterHUB. Data can be

exported to NetCDF, Zarr, or CSV. The *climakitae* export function will also inform the user when the data is very large or will fill up the drive that is targeted. Here is a sample workflow for exporting using *climakitae*:

```
None
import climakitae as ck
# NetCDF4 export locally
ck.export(data, filename="my_filename1", format="NetCDF")
# Zarr export locally
ck.export(data, filename="my_filename2", format="Zarr")
# CSV export locally
ck.export(data, filename="my_filename4", format="CSV")
```

Accessing or downloading data using Python intake package

As part of building *climakitae*, we created an [intake](#) data catalog, that allows for easy programmatic access to the data used on the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine, and is specifically an implementation of [intake-ESM](#), which is designed for climate data. This catalog can be opened using Python by knowing the URL of the catalog file.

Best Use

Accessing the cae-collection of data in Python without having to download the dataset completely. Allows for spatial and temporal filtering of the data before exporting to the local filesystem. It can also be used to analyze large datasets with xarray and dask, and to convert the data to NetCDF if there is sufficient memory.

Limitations

Can only help access data that is in the cae-collection intake catalog. Other datasets in the cadcat S3 bucket have to be referenced manually using this option. To access all the data in the bucket, look into using the next option, the *climakitae* python package.

Example Usage

First, install the prerequisites:

```
None
pip install intake-esm==2023.11.10 s3fs
```


Then open the intake-esm data catalog for querying:

```
None
import intake

cat = intake.open_esm_datastore(
    'https://cadcat.s3.amazonaws.com/cae-collection.json'
)
```

This json file stores all the metadata and paths to the data contained in the catalog and populates the intake database. To see the unique attributes contained in the catalog, run:

```
None
cat.unique()

# code output
activity_id                [LOCA2,
WRF]
institution_id             [UCSD, CAE,
UCLA]
source_id                  [ACCESS-CM2, CESM2-LENS, CNRM-ESM2-1,
EC-Earth...]
experiment_id              [historical, ssp245, ssp370, ssp585,
reanalysis]
member_id                  [r1i1p1f1, r2i1p1f1, r3i1p1f1, r10i1p1f1,
r4i1...]
table_id                   [day, mon, yrmax,
1hr]
variable_id                [hursmax, hursmin, huss, pr, rsds, tasmax,
tas...]
grid_label                 [d03, d01,
d02]
path                       [s3://cadcat/loca2/ucsd/access-cm2/historical/...
```



```
derived_variable_id
[]
```

The parameters on the left should look familiar from the discussion of the data directory structure at the beginning of this primer. Here is a table that describes what these parameters mean:

Familiar Name	CMIP6 Term
Downscaling Method	activity_id
Institution	institution_id
Source	source_id
Experiment	experiment_id
Variant	member_id
Frequency	table_id
Variable	variable_id
Resolution	grid_label

The intake-esm catalog can be filtered using the search method:

```
None
cat_subset = cat.search(activity_id="LOCA2")
cat_subset.unique()

# code output
activity_id
[LOCA2]
```



```

institution_id
[UCSD]

source_id          [ACCESS-CM2, CESM2-LENS, CNRM-ESM2-1,
EC-Earth...]

experiment_id     [historical, ssp245, ssp370,
ssp585]

member_id         [r1i1p1f1, r2i1p1f1, r3i1p1f1, r10i1p1f1,
r4i1...]

table_id          [day, mon,
yrmax]

variable_id       [hursmax, hursmin, huss, pr, rsds, tasmax,
tas...]

grid_label
[d03]

path
[s3://cadcat/loca2/ucsd/access-cm2/historical/...]

derived_variable_id
[]

cat_subset.unique()['source_id']

['ACCESS-CM2', 'CESM2-LENS', 'CNRM-ESM2-1', 'EC-Earth3',
'EC-Earth3-Veg', 'FGOALS-g3', 'GFDL-ESM4', 'HadGEM3-GC31-LL',
'INM-CM5-0', 'IPSL-CM6A-LR', 'KACE-1-0-G', 'MIROC6',
'MPI-ESM1-2-HR', 'MRI-ESM2-0', 'TaiESM1']

```

Further refinement of the catalog search supports finding a particular dataset using the available attributes (not all combinations are possible). The [AWS S3 Explorer](#) and the [Data Catalog](#) are useful for figuring out needed attributes:

```

None
cat_1model = cat.search(

```



```
activity_id="LOCA2",
source_id="ACCESS-CM2",
experiment_id="historical",
member_id="r1i1p1f1",
table_id="mon",
variable_id="tasmax"
)
```

This will narrow the catalog records to just one dataset. From there, these commands may be used to load the dataset:

```
None
dset_dict = cat_1model.to_dataset_dict(zarr_kwargs={'consolidated':
True}, storage_options={'anon': True})
ds = dset_dict['LOCA2.UCSD.ACCESS-CM2.historical.mon.d03']
```

Intake returns a dictionary of xarray datasets so that the catalog query may be used to return multiple datasets (such as getting historical and SSP's, or all models). In this case we have just one dataset and can pull it out of the dictionary and assign it to an object of its own. This object is a reference to the data, not the data itself. It can now be used to further filter and/or reshape the data if desired. To save the dataset as a NetCDF file, run this command:

```
None
ds.to_netcdf('LOCA2_UCSD_ACCESS-CM2_historical_mon_d03.nc',
encoding={k: {'zlib': True, 'complevel': 6} for k in ds})
```

Reading the catalog CSV and Zarrs from multiple languages

The [Intake-ESM Catalog CSV](#) file can be parsed and searched directly from many programming languages in addition to Python. From there, any of the datasets can be opened using languages with a [Zarr implementation](#), of which there are many to choose from.

Best Use

Programmatic access from multiple languages with a minimal number of dependencies.

Limitations

Any analysis is left as an exercise for the user, which isn't necessarily a limitation so much as an invitation to dive into the data.

Example Usage

Here is a JavaScript example using [Papa Parse](#) to read the CSV and [Zarr.js](#) to read a time series slice:

```
JavaScript
import Papa from 'papaparse';

import { slice, openArray } from 'zarr';

const baseURL = 'https://cadcat.s3-us-west-2.amazonaws.com/';

fetch(`${baseURL}cae-zarr.csv`).then(
  response => response.text()
).then(async text => {
  const csv = Papa.parse(text, {
    header: true,
    skipEmptyLines: true
  });

  const varname = 'tasmin';

  const records = csv.data.filter(rec =>
    rec.activity_id === 'LOCA2' && rec.variable_id === varname
  );

  const path = `${records[0].path.replace('s3://cadcat/', '')}${varname}`;

  const arr = await openArray({
    store: baseURL,
```



```
    path: path,  
    mode: 'r'  
  });  
  
  const arrSlice = await arr.get([null, 250, 250]);  
  
});
```

Accessing or downloading the AE data using Python xarray

Zarr stores are a cloud-optimized dataset that are designed to be opened and queried directly over the Internet. The most basic setup to access these Zarr stores is to simply open them in Python using [xarray](#). For more information on Zarr in xarray see: [Introduction to Zarr](#).

Best Use

This method is best suited for users with experience in Python and xarray who prefer a direct and streamlined approach rather than using higher-level tools such as *climakitae* or intake-esm. It provides the most expedient way to access Zarr datasets stored in S3.

Limitations

None really. However, users must know the dataset's location and handle all of the temporal and spatial filtering independently.

Example Usage

Starting from a clean Python environment, install the prerequisites using these commands:

```
None  
pip install numcodecs==0.14.1, '`xarray`[io,parallel]==2025.4.0',  
s3fs==2025.5.1
```

Then run a Python shell and run these commands to access the LOCA2 dataset:

```
None  
import xarray as xr  
ds = xr.open_zarr(  

```



```
's3://cadcat/loca2/ucsd/access-cm2/ssp370/r1i1p1f1/day/tasmax/d03/'
, storage_options={'anon': True}
)
```

The entire dataset can then be exported to NetCDF for conversion, but at least 6GB of free storage space is required. It is recommended to use some sort of compression algorithm when writing to NetCDF, otherwise it is uncompressed, and this can create very large datasets. Without compression, approximately 33GB of storage space is needed to store the NetCDF of this dataset. This is the command to save to NetCDF:

```
None
ds.to_netcdf('access-cm2_ssp370_r1i1p1f1_day_tasmax_d03.nc',
encoding={k: {'zlib': True, 'complevel': 6} for k in ds})
```

A more practical use case would be to temporally subset the dataset before exporting, such as a 30-year period ranging from 2045-2075. Filter the xarray dataset using this command:

```
None
# Temporally filter to 30 year period 2045-2075
ds = ds.sel(time=slice('2045', '2075'))
```

This will result in a more manageable 13GB uncompressed, or 2.3GB compressed dataset, but still large.

Downloading AE data using the AWS Command Line Interface (CLI)

The free [AWS Command Line Interface \(CLI\)](#) tool is useful for bulk downloading entire directory structures of data at once, or downloading Zarr stores (which are directory structures) to a local machine. The AWS CLI is an open source tool enabling the use of the command-line shell to access and interact with the [Analytics Engine S3 bucket directly](#). This tool simplifies downloading all the data in a dataset.

Best Use

Downloading large amounts of data, including multiple models, simulations, and/or resolutions. Can be configured to filter for specific models, variables, resolutions, etc., based on the storage “directory” structure of the data in S3.

Limitations

Must download the entire dataset, whether it is NetCDF or Zarr store. Can not spatially or temporally filter the data using AWS CLI, thus resulting in the possibility of downloading more data than is necessary. This solution does not require an Analytics Engine login but does require some familiarity with shell scripting.

Example Usage

Natively, AWS S3 does not store data in a traditional directory structure but instead uses keys to the binary data stored there. The AWS Explorer represents the data keys as directories for convenience. Users can first utilize either the [AWS Explorer](#) or [Data Catalog](#) to find the path to the data of interest. The following is an example of listing the bucket data using AWS CLI to display the variables available for this model:

```
None
# LOCA2 NetCDF

aws s3 ls --no-sign-request
s3://cadcat/loca2/aaa-ca-hybrid/MIROC6/0p0625deg/r1i1p1f1/ssp370/

# WRF Zarr

aws s3 ls --no-sign-request s3://cadcat/wrf/ucla/miroc6/ssp370/day/
```

The `--no-sign-request` option is required to access this public S3 bucket. Also notice the “s3://cadcat” URI is used instead of <https://cadcat.s3.amazonaws.com/>. S3 has its own protocol for accessing data, but users can examine the directory structure as shown above to find the path or can locate the S3 protocol path using the [Data Catalog](#). Note the difference in “directory” structure in the two commands above between the NetCDF and Zarr data. It is important to remember that with the NetCDF, there is only one resolution, but with the Zarr data there are up to three resolutions for each variable.

Given the amount of data available, this command will return a large number of variable directories. The ideal approach to manage the size of data requested is to determine which SSP, ensemble member, temporal frequency, variables, and resolution are of interest to avoid downloading an extremely large dataset.

NetCDF data is contained within a single `.nc` file in a directory, while Zarr stores contain directories within `.zattrs`, `.zgroup`, and `.zmetadata` – all data at and below that directory are the Zarr data. To download a single NetCDF variable or a single Zarr store here are the AWS CLI commands:

```
None
# LOCA2 NetCDF
```



```
aws s3 cp
s3://cadcat/loca2/aaa-ca-hybrid/MIROC6/0p0625deg/r1i1p1f1/ssp370/ta
smax loca2/aaa-ca-hybrid/MIROC6/0p0625deg/r1i1p1f1/ssp370/tasmax
--no-sign-request --recursive

# LOCA2 Zarr

aws s3 cp
s3://cadcat/loca2/ucsd/fgoals-g3/ssp585/r1i1p1f1/mon/tasmax/d03/
loca2/ucsd/fgoals-g3/ssp585/r1i1p1f1/mon/tasmax/d03/
--no-sign-request --recursive

# WRF Zarr

aws s3 cp s3://cadcat/wrf/ucla/cesm2/historical/day/rh/d02/
wrf/ucla/cesm2/historical/day/rh/d02/ --no-sign-request --recursive
```

This will synchronize the directory structure in S3 to a local directory. The second path entry in the command can be changed to another path on a local system. The `--recursive` option is required otherwise there will be a key error as the “directory” path itself does not exist in S3.

Using the above command and changing the paths allows users to download many datasets from S3, but be aware that these data can get extremely large. There is almost 1 petabyte of data stored in the cadcat S3 bucket, and an hourly, 3-km WRF variable Zarr store is about 219GB for a single GCM/SSP combination.

AWS CLI can be used to find out the size of the download before actually syncing the data to a local machine:

```
None
# Calculate size of data on S3

aws s3 ls --summarize --human-readable --recursive
--no-sign-request s3://cadcat/wrf/ucla/miroc6/ssp370/1hr/t2/d03

# This will return 207GB
```

A safer, more strategic way to download multiple datasets, whether NetCDF or Zarr, is to write a script that loops through the parameters of interest and targets the specific path to each dataset. The following example downloads the three NetCDF files containing the SSP370 LOCA2 data totaling 8GB. The AWS command may be combined with bash scripting (or some other form of scripting/programming language) to download a variable for multiple models:

None

```
# LOCA2 NetCDF

activities=("MIROC6" "GFDL-ESM4")

for a in $activities; do

aws s3 cp
s3://cadcat/loca2/aaa-ca-hybrid/$a/0p0625deg/r1i1p1f1/ssp370/tasmax
loca2/aaa-ca-hybrid/$a/0p0625deg/r1i1p1f1/ssp370/tasmax
--no-sign-request --recursive

done
```

An alternative to looping in scripts is to use the `--include` and `--exclude` flags in AWS CLI. To access all available models for a particular variable, add the variable name with wildcards to match files based on that pattern.

None

```
aws s3 cp s3://cadcat/loca2/aaa-ca-hybrid . --no-sign-request
--recursive --exclude '*' --include '*tasmax*'
```

If there is sufficient file storage for 12.7TB (12,700GB), it is possible to download the entire LOCA2 NetCDF data store using the following command:

None

```
# !!CAUTION!! This command will download 12.7TB of data!

aws s3 cp s3://cadcat/loca2/aaa-ca-hybrid /my/local/path
--no-sign-request --recursive
```

Accessing or downloading AE data using the *climakitaegui* Python package

There is an additional Python package, called *climakitaegui*, that when used with *climakitae* allows the user to call interactive menus to retrieve data. The graphical user interfaces are built in [Panel](#), which is a system designed to build dashboards and visualizations in Python and is part of the [HoloViz](#) ecosystem.

Best Use

Retrieving an xarray `DataArray` within a Jupyter notebook environment when not familiar with using the `get_data` functionality within *climakitae*. The GUI allows you to retrieve data in different forms than the original source material. This could be by warming level, as a derived variable, a timeseries concatenation of historical modeled and future scenarios, or as a concatenation of multiple simulations.

Limitations

Some processing is done on original data, such as concatenating multiple simulations together and adding additional metadata, and it is returned as `DataArray`. Requires a graphical environment to run the interface.

Example Usage

The easiest way to use *climakitaegui* is to use it inside a Jupyter notebook. The steps for setting up a Python environment with Jupyter notebooks and then installing *climakitaegui* are detailed in this [Wiki](#). Then import *climakitae*:

```
None
import `climakitae` as ck
import `climakitaegui` as ckg
```

Once imported, call the global method `Select` to create the menu interface and then use the `show` method to bring up the visual interface:

```
None
selections = ckg.Select()
selections.show()
```

This will bring up an interface that looks like this:

Data Options in the Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine

Data Type:
 Gridded
 Stations

Approach:
 Time
 Warming Level

Downscaling Method:
 Dynamical
 Statistical
 Dynamical+Statistical

Variable Type:
 Variable
 Station

Air Temperature at 2m

Temperature of the air 2m above Earth's surface. This is the standard measure of air temperature used for most modeling applications and is also referred to as "Ambient Temperature".

Variable Units:
 K
 degC
 degF

Timescale:
 daily
 monthly
 hourly

Model Grid Spacing:
 3 km
 9 km
 45 km

WARMING LEVELS APPROACH: Options only valid if retrieval method is set to "Warming Level"

Years around Global Warming Level (+/-): Warming Level (°C):
 e.g. 15 means a 30yr window

15

TIME-BASED APPROACH: Options only valid if retrieval method is set to "Time"

Years: How do you want to time-slice the data?

1980 .. 2015

Historical Data:
 Estimates of recent historical climatic conditions

Historical Climate
 Historical Reconstruction

Future Model Data:
 Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) represent different global emissions scenarios

SSP 2-4.5
 SSP 3-7.0
 SSP 5-8.5

Historical

1950 2000 2050 2100

Location Options for the Selected Data

Stations:
 Set data type to 'Station' to see options

9 km

Subset the data by...

Location selection

Latitude: 32.50 .. 42

Longitude: -125.50 .. -114

Compute an area average across grid cells within your selected region?
 Yes No

Include cells touching edge of the selection area

This allows a user to interactively select the various attributes to refine the datasets. Logic is built into the menu to filter out implausible combinations. Users can filter on time period, simulation(s), and spatially using the built-in geographies. Selected data can then be retrieved using:

```
None
data_to_use = selections.retrieve()
```

Accessing Zarr data directly using QGIS 3.40.10+

The free and open source Geographical Information System software package QGIS can open Zarr stores stored in S3 directly. The 3.40.10 version of QGIS or later is required for this functionality. Note that this option only works for smaller files such as aggregated monthly data, GWL, or climate indices. QGIS can only access datasets with a limited number of raster bands, so hourly or daily data have too many bands to load successfully.

Best Use

Loading CA:AE Zarrs directly from S3 should be limited to datasets represented by warming level (as with the example below) or with a monthly time frequency. Daily or hourly datasets have too many bands to be loaded directly into QGIS.

Limitations

GDAL, which underpins QGIS, has a default limit of 65,000 bands for reading raster layers. This is to prevent excess memory consumption. This makes it not possible to load hourly or daily data, as the QGIS driver does not allow spatial or temporal filtering upon definition of the data connection.

Example Usage

To open the S3 Zarr store go to the menu item Layer→Add Layer→Add Raster Layer. This will bring up the Data Source Manager | Raster interface. Under Source Type switch the radio button to Protocol: HTTP(S), cloud, etc. then under the Protocol section choose AWS S3 for the Type, cadcat for the Bucket or container, and then enter the relative path to the Zarr store, which can be found by using the [AWS Explorer](#) or [Data Catalog](#).. As an example to load the multi-model mean extreme heat absolute Zarr store, which is stored at various warming levels enter “tmp/era/wrf/cae/mm4mean/ssp370/gwl/TX99p/d03/” for Object Key.

The screenshot shows the 'Data Source Manager | Raster' dialog box in QGIS. The 'Source Type' is set to 'Protocol: HTTP(S), cloud, etc.'. Under the 'Protocol' section, 'Type' is 'AWS S3', 'Bucket or container' is 'cadcat', and 'Object key' is 'tmp/era/wrf/cae/mm4mean/ssp370/gwl/TX99p/d03/'. The 'Options' section is expanded, showing various settings like LIST_ALL_ARRAYS, USE_ZMETADATA, CACHE_TILE_PRESENCE, CACHE_KERCHUNK_JSON, MULTIBAND, DIM_X, DIM_Y, and LOAD_EXTRA_DIM_METADATA_DELAY, all set to '<Default>'. The 'Add' button is highlighted.

Clicking the Add button will bring up another menu. Select the variable name, in this case, TX99p. The shape of the array can be seen in the description with 472 by 223 spatial cells and 5 warming level bands.

This dataset is in Lambert Conformal projection used by WRF data. Here is the proj4 description of the custom projection:

None

```
+proj=lcc +lat_0=38 +lon_0=-70 +lat_1=30 +lat_2=60 +x_0=0 +y_0=0
+R=6370000 +units=m +no_defs +type=crs
```

And the WKT projection definition:

None

```
PROJCRS["undefined",
  BASEGEOGCRS["undefined",
    DATUM["undefined",
      ELLIPSOID["undefined", 6370000, 0,
        LENGTHUNIT["metre", 1,
          ID["EPSG", 9001]]]],
    PRIMEM["Greenwich", 0,
      ANGLEUNIT["degree", 0.0174532925199433],
      ID["EPSG", 8901]]],
  ID["EPSG", 9001]]],
```



```
CONVERSION["unnamed",
  METHOD["Lambert Conic Conformal (2SP)",
    ID["EPSG", 9802]],
  PARAMETER["Latitude of 1st standard parallel", 30,
    ANGLEUNIT["degree", 0.0174532925199433],
    ID["EPSG", 8823]],
  PARAMETER["Latitude of 2nd standard parallel", 60,
    ANGLEUNIT["degree", 0.0174532925199433],
    ID["EPSG", 8824]],
  PARAMETER["Latitude of false origin", 38,
    ANGLEUNIT["degree", 0.0174532925199433],
    ID["EPSG", 8821]],
  PARAMETER["Longitude of false origin", -70,
    ANGLEUNIT["degree", 0.0174532925199433],
    ID["EPSG", 8822]],
  PARAMETER["Easting at false origin", 0,
    LENGTHUNIT["metre", 1],
    ID["EPSG", 8826]],
  PARAMETER["Northing at false origin", 0,
    LENGTHUNIT["metre", 1],
    ID["EPSG", 8827]]],
CS[Cartesian, 2],
  AXIS["easting", east,
    ORDER[1],
    LENGTHUNIT["metre", 1,
      ID["EPSG", 9001]]],
```



```
AXIS["northing",north,  
ORDER[2],  
LENGTHUNIT["metre",1,  
ID["EPSG",9001]]]]
```

LOCA2 data is loaded in WGS84 (EPSG:4326), which is automatically handled by QGIS.

By default, QGIS will symbolize the Zarr as a Multiband Color raster with the first 3 GWLs as bands. Double-click on the raster layer in the Layers pane to bring up the Symbology menu, then switch Render Type to Singleband pseudocolor. Then pick the band which represents the GWL of interest and hit Ok.

Downloading LOCA2 NetCDF data using the Cal-Adapt Data Download Tool

The [Cal-Adapt Data Download Tool \(DDT\)](#) allows users to easily download data packages of LOCA2 data, specifically the data in [loca2/aaa-ca-hybrid](#). These data packages are pre-made groups or clusters of statistically downscaled LOCA2 data that are most commonly accessed on Cal-Adapt, which helps make data selection and download more intuitive and user-friendly.

Best Use

Downloading LOCA2 NetCDF data in bulk with the ability to temporally aggregate (Monthly) and spatially filter by county. Can download multiple scenarios, models, and metrics (variables) at once.

Limitations

Currently limited to the LOCA2 NetCDF datasets only. In addition, currently users are required to spatially filter by one or more counties, so they can not easily get the entire spatial extent of the data.

Example Usage

1. Navigate to the Data Download Tool:
2. Click the "Customize and Download" button under the data package of choice.
3. Make custom selections in the "Review Your Data Package" sidebar including what frequency, which models, variables, and counties the user is interested in downloading.
4. Click "Download Your Data" to create the data packages which are ready for download to a local machine.

Downloading LOCA2 NetCDF data using the AWS Explorer web page

Anyone can utilize existing AWS explorer functions within the [Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine S3 bucket](#) to explore and download existing data through a web browser. Data can be accessed by navigating the file

structure to identify and download NetCDF files to a local computer. This solution does not require an Analytics Engine login and does not require coding.

Best Use

Since web browsers only allow download of individual files rather than whole directory structures, the AWS Explorer is best used only for downloading NetCDF files in [loca2/aaa-ca-hybrid](#), and in this capacity, it would be better to use the AWS CLI toolset for downloading more than a few files.

Limitations

Can only download files separately and does not preserve the directory structure they are housed in S3.

Metadata Standards

Topics covered:

- Why use **standard conventions** for organizing data products and associated metadata?
- Best practices for **GIS data formats**
- Best practices for **NetCDF data formats**
- **Contributing** or **requesting datasets** on the Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine

Why use standard conventions for organizing data products and associated metadata?

Readability. Modern conventions are designed in a way that metadata is readable by humans and concurrently organized in a way that can be read by computers.

Interoperability. Data developed to support state energy-related climate research and planning should be easily accessed by research partners on California's climate assessments, national climate assessments [which utilize similar conventions](#), and global climate modeling efforts (i.e. CMIP). The end goal is allow a user to incorporate data from multiple data sources directly on Analytics Engine, without the need for customization.

Public Availability. In order to work within the wide range of data serving options and analytics tools on Analytics Engine (interactive programming environments, direct downloads) input data must be in formats which can be incorporated into Analytics Engine, and directly read in by end users who may work with the data in the cloud computing environment or download the data directly.

Documentation. Datasets hosted on Analytics Engine should be self-describing, each dataset should contain information about when the product was produced, which version of the dataset is being used, what data went into the data product, relevant references and points of contact for questions about the data.

Best Practices for GIS Data Formats

All geospatial datasets should include relevant metadata adhering to the [Content Standard for Digital Geospatial Metadata](#) by the Federal Geographic Data Committee (FGDC). While the specification may appear complex to newcomers, the goal is to communicate basic information about the data that makes it more transparent and usable for downstream end users.

At a bare minimum, the title, originator contact, and citation details must be provided. Additionally, the abstract and purpose sections should be completed with a concise narrative and intention behind the data. The entity and attribute information needs to provide descriptions of the variables and values present, such as coded classifications, entity types, and domains. Desktop GIS applications like ArcGIS and QGIS assist in authoring and automating metadata generation, avoiding the need to edit the XML source. A validation service is available from [USGS](#).

Best Practices for NetCDF

NetCDF files should be generated so as to be easily transferred between data producer and end user, and self-describing so that extensive documentation files are not needed. Metadata included with a netCDF file should be easy to read by users but also formatted in a way that present day software can read.

Data or products hosted on the platform as a netCDF file should follow [standard best practices as established by Unidata](#), including using a standard convention for organizing and describing data products. [CF Conventions](#) are preferred because it includes categories of nearly all relevant topics (i.e. atmospheric, hydrology, ocean/lake, surface conditions), but for datasets outside these topics [alternative conventions](#) will be considered. Adoption of CF conventions assures end users can use netCDF products developed by CEC supported research using only information contained within the netCDF.

Minimum specifications

Each NetCDF should contain the following components at a minimum:

Convention. List the standard convention used to organize the data. [CF Convention](#) is preferred.

Coordinate System. Dimensions of time and space should be included as standalone variables, each self-described using a standard convention system, including a description of the units and a naming attribute (i.e. for latitude units of “degrees_north” and a long_name of “grid latitude, positive northward”). Coordinate variables should not contain missing values.

Variables.

1. *Variable Naming.* Whenever possible units should be named using industry standard names for interoperability. Naming variables (and their attributes) in conformation to the [Udunits package](#) will allow users of common open access software and packages to load in netCDF files directly, without extensive modification. This is critically important for data being uploaded onto the Analytics Engine.
2. *Variable Attributes.* At a minimum, variable attributes should contain units and a long name descriptor (e.g. descriptive enough to label plots).
3. *Missing Data.* A fill value or valid_range attribute should be applied to any variable with missing data.

Time Coordinates. Time variable should represent time elapsed since a reference date. Either Gregorian or Julian calendar dates could be used, but Gregorian is preferred as it is supported by more software platforms. Storing the data as an ISO 8601 object allows for easy reading and interpretation by users, as well as a robust interface for interaction with modern software. The [Udunits package](#) provides easy to use tools for encoding of dates.

Suggested practices

NetCDF Version. NetCDF-4 is the preferred and currently supported version.

Packing of Large Datasets. Large datasets may be condensed in size via packing, or a reduction in precision through use of a scale factor and offset value. Most modern netCDF tools and software automatically unpack data during load commands.

Global Attributes. Global attributes describe the netCDF file and more broadly the research project and dataset itself, rather than a component of the netCDF file. Following CF Convention standard best practices, we encourage the inclusion of the following fields as Global Attributes:

Field	Description
Title	What is in the file
Institution	Where it was produced
Source	How it was produced (e.g. model version, instrument type)
References	Audit trail of processing operations
History	Pointers to publications or web documentation
Comment	Miscellaneous

Test for Compliance. Before submission of the netCDF product, consider using an [online test](#) for your data product.

Contributing or requesting datasets on the Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine

Users of the Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine may request the addition of datasets to the platform for use in the cloud computing environment, which will be approved on a case-by-case basis. Users who would like to submit a dataset are responsible for ensuring any new data conforms to the standards described above. Requests for particular datasets should be submitted via email, including citation information if applicable and a description of the intended use of the dataset.